

Oxidation of some α,β -unsaturated compounds by bromate ion in hydrochloric acid medium

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Manuscript received 16 December 2000, revised 3 August 2001, accepted 29 August 2001

The oxidation kinetics of some α,β -unsaturated compounds, $\text{CH}_2=\text{CHX}$ ($\text{X} = \text{COOH}, \text{CONH}_2, \text{CN}$) by potassium bromate in hydrochloric acid medium have been studied. The activation parameters of the reactions have been evaluated. The reactivity of the α,β -unsaturated compounds is as follows : $\text{COOH} < \text{CONH}_2 < \text{CN}$. A mechanism involving the formation of an unstable bromate ester which decomposes to the reaction products has been suggested.

A considerable amount of information is available on the mechanism of oxidation of unsaturated compounds towards different oxidants, such as potassium permanganate¹ and chromic acid². The oxidations of cinnamic acid were carried out using permanganate in acid medium³. The osmium(VIII)-catalyzed oxidations of cinnamic and crotonic acids by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III)⁴ and quinolinium dichromate⁵ have also been studied. The oxidations of styrene and substituted styrenes to corresponding benzaldehyde were also studied by hexacyanoferrate(III)⁶ and by quinolinium dichromate⁷. Other studies pertaining to the oxidation of styrene include oxidants such as chromyl chloride in carbon tetrachloride⁸, thallium(III) nitrate in methanol⁹, lead(IV)¹⁰ and cobalt(III)¹¹. The oxidations of 3-buten-2-ol and 2-buten-1-ol by palladium(II)¹² in aqueous solution were also studied. The oxidation of alkenes with OsO_4 to give *cis*-diols is a well established reaction¹³. There is no literature data to date concerning the oxidation of α,β -unsaturated compounds by bromate ion. Potassium bromate is a powerful oxidizing agent¹⁴ in acid solution. The reduction potential of $\text{BrO}_3^-/\text{Br}^-$ is 1.52 V at 25°. The bromate ion oxidation of metal ion has been studied with different inorganic reductants¹⁵. The oxidations of some alcohols^{16,17}, aromatic aldehydes¹⁸ and α -hydroxy acids¹⁹ by bromate were investigated in acid media. An attempt has been made to study the oxidative behavior and their relative reactivities of some α,β -unsaturated compounds towards bromate ion in acid medium.

Results and Discussion

The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were determined at different $[\text{BrO}_3^-]$ in the region $(5.0\text{--}20.0) \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³ but at constant $[\text{CH}_2=\text{CHX}]$, $[\text{H}^+]$ and tempera-

Table 1. Variation of pseudo-first order rate constants for BrO_3^- with substrate (S) concentrations at different temperatures*

Temp. K	$[\text{S}] \times 10^2$ mol dm ⁻³	$k_{\text{obs}}^a \times 10^4$ s ⁻¹	$k_{\text{obs}}^b \times 10^4$ s ⁻¹	$k_{\text{obs}}^c \times 10^4$ s ⁻¹
303	2.5	1.53 (6.12)	2.05 (8.20)	2.82 (11.3)
	5.0	2.89 (5.80)	4.06 (8.10)	5.59 (11.2)
	10.0	5.72 (5.72)	8.28 (8.24)	11.2 (11.2)
	15.0	8.75 (5.83)	12.3 (8.20)	16.4 (11.3)
	20.0	11.8 (5.90)	16.5 (8.25)	22.1 (11.0)
	25.0	14.5 (5.80)	20.8 (8.32)	28.0 (11.2)
308	2.5	2.28 (9.12)	3.09 (12.40)	4.18 (16.7)
	5.0	4.48 (8.96)	6.32 (12.60)	8.29 (16.6)
	10.0	9.68 (9.68)	12.7 (12.7)	16.68 (16.7)
	15.0	13.9 (9.26)	19.1 (12.70)	24.8 (16.3)
	20.0	19.0 (9.50)	25.2 (12.60)	32.8 (16.4)
	25.0	22.8 (9.12)	31.1 (12.40)	41.6 (16.6)
313	2.5	3.68 (14.7)	4.73 (18.90)	5.87 (23.5)
	5.0	7.23 (14.5)	9.79 (19.60)	12.1 (24.2)
	10.0	14.4 (14.4)	19.4 (19.40)	24.0 (24.0)
	15.0	21.7 (14.5)	28.8 (19.20)	35.2 (23.5)
	20.0	28.5 (14.2)	37.9 (18.90)	48.2 (24.1)
	25.0	34.4 (13.7)	46.7 (18.70)	59.2 (23.7)
318	2.5	5.37 (21.5)	7.16 (28.60)	8.78 (35.1)
	5.0	10.2 (20.4)	14.4 (28.80)	17.1 (34.2)
	10.0	21.4 (21.4)	28.1 (28.10)	33.9 (33.9)
	15.0	32.1 (21.4)	42.4 (28.30)	49.8 (33.2)
	20.0	42.6 (21.3)	57.3 (28.60)	69.1 (34.5)
	25.0	53.7 (21.5)	71.6 (28.60)	82.9 (33.2)

* $\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCOOH}$. ^b $\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCONH}_2$. ^c $\text{CH}_2=\text{CHCN}$.

*Figures in the parentheses represent the values of second order rate constant ($k_2 \times 10^3$ dm³ mol⁻¹).

ture of 1.0×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³, 1.0 mol dm⁻³ and 30^8 K, respectively. The values of k_{obs} are $(9.65 \pm 3.0) \times 10^{-4}$, $(12.8 \pm 0.4) \times 10^{-4}$ and $(16.8 \pm 0.5) \times 10^{-4}$ s⁻¹ for the oxidation of acrylic acid, acrylamide and acrylonitrile, respectively. The pseudo-first order rate constants were also determined at different [CH₂=CHX] but at constant [BrO₃], [H⁺] and temperature. The results are recorded in Table 1. The plots of k_{obs} vs [substrate] are linear and pass through the origin. The quotients $k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{CH}_2=\text{CHX}]$ as recorded in Table 1 further indicates that the order with respect to [CH₂=CHX] is unity.

The influence of hydrogen ion dependence on the pseudo-first order rate constants was studied over a wide range of [H⁺] but at constant ionic strength of 1.0 mol dm⁻³ adjusted by the addition of sodium chloride. The results recorded in Table 2 indicate that the order with respect to [H⁺] is unity for each reaction. The reactions were studied at constant [BrO₃], [substrate], [H⁺] and 308 K, at different [Cl⁻] $(0.6-4.0) \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³ which was varied by the addition of NaCl. The values of k_{obs} were found to be independent of sodium chloride concentrations.

Table 2. Effect of [H⁺] on pseudo-first order rate constant*

[CH₂=CHX] = 5.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [BrO₃] = 1.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³,

Temp. = 308 K

[H ⁺] mol dm ⁻³	$k_{\text{obs}}^a \times 10^4$ s ⁻¹	$k_{\text{obs}}^b \times 10^4$ s ⁻¹	$k_{\text{obs}}^c \times 10^4$ s ⁻¹
0.1	0.497 (4.97)	0.651 (6.50)	0.829 (8.30)
0.2	0.852 (4.26)	1.36 (6.80)	1.65 (8.20)
0.3	1.33 (4.43)	1.89 (6.30)	2.48 (8.20)
0.4	1.75 (4.37)	2.53 (6.30)	3.31 (8.30)
0.5	2.22 (4.40)	3.14 (6.30)	4.16 (8.30)
0.6	2.68 (4.46)	3.79 (6.30)	5.00 (8.30)
0.7	3.16 (4.50)	4.36 (6.20)	5.75 (8.20)
0.8	3.63 (4.53)	5.02 (6.20)	6.56 (8.20)
0.9	4.03 (4.70)	5.60 (6.20)	7.51 (8.30)
1.0	4.52 (4.50)	6.19 (6.20)	8.34 (8.30)

^aCH₂=CHCOOH. ^bCH₂=CHCONH₂. ^cCH₂=CHCN.

*Figures in the parentheses represent the values of $k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{H}^+] \times 10^4$ dm³ mol⁻¹.

The influence of temperature on the rate was determined for each reaction. The values of k_3 ($k_3 = k_{\text{obs}} / [\text{substrate}] [\text{H}^+]$) were calculated at different temperatures from 303 to 318 K. The activation enthalpy (ΔH^\ddagger) was calculated from the linear plots of $\log k_3/T$ vs $1/T$ followed by the estimation of entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) from theory of absolute reaction rate as mentioned earlier²⁰. Thermodynamic values are recorded in Table 3. The enthalpy of activation has been found to be linearly related to entropy of activa-

tion. The isokinetic temperature has been calculated to be 352 K. The linear plot indicates that a similar mechanism may be operative in all the reactions. The isokinetic behavior is also supported by the Exner plot of $\log k_3$ vs $\log k_3'$, where k_3 and k_3' are the rate constants at 303 (T_1) and 308 K (T_2), respectively. The isokinetic temperature²¹ (β) has been calculated from the relation, $\beta = T_1 T_2 (1 - f)/(T_1 - T_2 f)$, where f is the slope of the Exner plot. The value has been found to be 357 K, and is higher than T , the mid-point of the experimentally used range of temperature. The value of $\beta - T$ which is positive, indicates that the reactions are governed by their enthalpies of activation in the temperature range studied²².

Table 3. Values of activation parameters of the oxidations of α,β -unsaturated compounds

Substrate	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
CH ₂ =CHCOOH	67 ± 2	-67 ± 7
CH ₂ =CHCONH ₂	64 ± 2	-74 ± 7
CH ₂ =CHCN	57 ± 4	-95 ± 13

The rate of the reaction was found to be dependent on the concentrations of substrate and oxidant. This kinetic behavior is consistent with a mechanism involving a rate-determining reaction between α,β -unsaturated compound and bromate. The rate increases with increase in [H⁺]. The order with respect to [H⁺] is found to be one in each reaction. This indicates that HBrO₃ which is formed by the reaction between BrO₃⁻ and H⁺ (step 1), reacts with the substrate,

There have been earlier reports of the involvement of such HBrO₃ species in aromatic aldehyde oxidations¹⁸. The reactions obey the rate expression,

$$\frac{-d[\text{Bromate}]}{dt} = k_3 [\text{Bromate}] [\text{CH}_2=\text{CHX}] [\text{H}^+] \quad (2)$$

The kinetic data suggest the compatibility of attack of the HBrO₃ on the α,β -unsaturated compounds to form a carbonium ion A which then reacts with a nucleophile (e.g. water) in the reaction mixture to form an intermediate B. In the presence of water and excess HBrO₃, the intermediate B could be converted to the cyclic bromate ester C. This ester is then cleaved to give the glycol I. There is considerable use for HOCl and hypochlorite in the manufacture of α -glycol²³. The reactivity of α,β -unsaturated compound follows the order: COOH < CONH₂ < CN. The higher rate of oxidation obtained with acetonitrile is to be expected since the presence of CN group will facilitate the formation of intermediate bromate ester, thereby increasing the reaction rate. The steps of reactions are shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

HBrO_2 which is formed (Scheme 1) is then reduced to HBr through successive steps by excess substrates to give product diol. The steps of the reactions are as follows :

The intermediate glycol, by reacting with HBrO_3 is then rapidly converted to aldehydes and HBrO_2 according to the Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

HBrO_2 and HOBr react with diol to give the reaction products as shown in steps in steps (5) and (6),

Effort to isolate the intermediate I during the course of the reaction was not successful. It is suggested that the glycol I, which is formed during the reaction is rapidly converted by the oxidant, in acid medium, to yield formaldehyde as the product. Again in addition to formaldehyde, XCHO ($\text{X} = \text{CN}, \text{CONH}_2$ and COOH) is also formed. However, the product having CN or CONH_2 groups gives glyoxylic acid on hydrolysis^{24a}. The latter subsequently, on decarboxylation^{24b} in acetic acid, gives another molecule of formaldehyde. Although all the reactions have been shown to occur through intermediate compound formation, the kinetic evidence for intermediate compound was not significant unlike the oxidations of α -hydroxy acids and polyhydroxy compounds by this oxidant. The activation parameters obtained in the oxidations of the number of or-

ganic compounds by this oxidant have been compiled and an attempt has been made to correlate the results of the oxidation reaction (Fig. 1). The proposed mechanism is supported by the value of the activation parameters (Table 3). The moderately large negative values of entropies of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) suggest that the transition state formed is considerably rigid, resulting in a reduction in the degrees of freedom of the molecules. The similarity in ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger values emphasizes the probability that all of these reactions involve similar rate-determining step.

Fig. 1. Plots of ΔS^\ddagger vs ΔH^\ddagger for the oxidation of some α,β -unsaturated compounds by bromate ion : (1) acrylic acid, (2) acrylamide, (3) acrylonitrile, (4) methanol, (5) ethanol, (6) isopropanol, (7) benzyl alcohol, (8) propan-2-ol, (9) 1-phenylethanol, (10) diphenylmethanol, (11) ethylene glycol, (12) *meso*-butane-2,3-diol, (13) pinacol, (14) dihydrobenzoin, (15) benzopinacol, (16) lactic acid, (17) α -hydroxyisobutyric acid, (18) atolactic acid, (19) mandelic acid, (20) benzilic acid, (21) 9-hydroxy-9-carboxyfluorine, (22) malic acid, (23) tartaric acid, (24) citric acid, (25) glucose, (26) mannose, (27) galactose, (28) xylose, (29) arabinose, (30) ribose, (31) erythrose, (32) glyceraldehyde, (33) glycolaldehyde, (34) glucosamine hydrochloride, (35) mannosamine hydrochloride, (36) galactosamine hydrochloride. Substrates : Vinyl compounds (present study), alcohols^{16,17,28}, diols¹⁷, α -hydroxy acids¹⁹, aldoses²⁰, amino sugars²⁹

Experimental

Acrylic acid (Merck) and acrylonitrile (S.M. India) were purified by distillation prior to use. Acrylamide (S.M. India) was used as supplied. Potassium bromate (AnalaR) was used. All solutions of α,β -unsaturated compounds and potassium bromate were prepared in double-distilled water prepared by refluxing over potassium permanganate. All other inorganic compounds were of the highest purity available.

IR spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer 298 spectrometer. C, H and N were analysed using a Perkin-Elmer 240 Analyser. M.p. was determined using a Galenkamp apparatus.

Rate measurements : The rate of decrease of bromate was followed titrimetrically. Solution of BrO_3^- and the mixture containing $\text{CH}_2=\text{CHX}$, H^+ and $\text{Hg}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ were separately thermostated. During the oxidation, interference by the liberated bromine was prevented by adding a calculated quantity of mercuric acetate which is inert towards the oxidation of α,β -unsaturated compounds. The reaction was initiated by adding oxidant to the mixture containing substrate, acid and mercuric acetate, and was followed by withdrawing aliquots of the reaction mixture at different intervals of time and quenching the reaction by adding it to an excess of potassium iodide solution. The liberated iodine was titrated against sodium thiosulfate solution using starch as an indicator and the pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were calculated. The duplicate experiments were always reproducible to $\pm 5\%$.

Product analysis : The reaction mixture containing an excess of $\text{CH}_2=\text{CHX}$ over the oxidant under kinetic condition was allowed to stand for 30 min. The product solution was then divided in two parts. One part of the reaction mixture was treated with 12 N H_2SO_4 (2 ml) and a little solid chromotropic acid and heated for 10 min in a water-bath at 60° . The pinkish violet colour indicated the presence of formaldehyde²⁵. Another part was treated with an excess of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazinehydrochloride solution, then heated on steam-bath for 5 min and left at room temperature for 1 h when the yellow crystals of the 2,4-DNP derivative of the product was obtained. The crystals were washed with water, dried, crystallized from ethanol and dried and m.p. $\approx 166-168^{\circ 26}$ (Found: C, 40.05; H, 2.8; N, 25.8. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$ calcd. for: C, 40.0; H, 2.85; N, 26.6%). The absence of IR bands²⁷ due to CN, CONH_2 and COOH of the 2,4-DNP derivative of the respective products further supports that XCHO which are formed in Scheme 2 and steps (5) and (6) are finally converted to give HCHO.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance to one of the authors (K.K.S.G.).

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